

NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF SHAPE FIXABILITY OF CONTINUOUS FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTICS

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SUMMARY: Continuous fibre-reinforced thermoplastic (CFRT) sheet materials have enjoyed a steady rise in popularity over recent times which can be largely attributed to the way they lend themselves to low-cycle-time manufacturing applications. In many of these rapid forming operations the actual process cycle is dominated by the time required to cool the moulded component to an appropriate final temperature. In such processes, the applied surface cooling rate can have a significant influence on the geometric conformance of the component as well as its internal stress state. This paper examines the applicability of the finite element (FE) method to predict the effects of a number of different cooling scenarios on the distortion incurred during the most commonly encountered deformation process in sheet forming, bending. A finite element model is developed to investigate the springforward phenomenon in composite sections which are subject to various cooling rates. The model goes some way toward accounting for the temperature dependent material property variation during cooling. Finally the results obtained from the numerical model are compared to those achieved from experiments. The implications of these results are discussed in the context of real manufacturing processes, such as deep drawing and roll forming.

KEYWORDS: springforward, shape fixability, cooling rate, continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic, finite elements, roll forming.

INTRODUCTION

Continuous fibre-reinforced thermoplastic composites have established themselves as tough, reliable, cost effective alternatives to various other traditional structural materials such as aluminum and even their thermosetting cousins. Their most significant advantage lies in their ability to undergo rapid curing cycles from the melt which are largely dependent on the temperature and only moderately dependent on any chemistry effects. This unique characteristic has provided the opportunity to apply rapid and economical manufacturing methods along the same lines as those used in one of the most pervasive of all manufacturing industries - sheet metal forming.

Already a good deal of success has been achieved in the development of fast, efficient, processing methods which go some way to realising the full benefits of thermoplastic composite materials [1,2]. An example of one of these processes is roll forming [3], which is presently in the early stages of development, but has already demonstrated the potential for continuous production at relatively high line speeds. Figure 1 demonstrates some of the possible profiles which may be achieved ranging from simple open sections to more complex closed sections. One key area of concern though in a process like roll forming is the development of residual stress and distortion in a formed components as they cool from the forming temperature. The elevated processing temperatures, and the large differences which exist between the thermoelastic properties of the matrix and fibres in directional polymeric composites leads to an inevitable build up of residual stress and subsequent distortion during cooling. The deviation from a components intended shape can render it useless, while the residual stress state can act to severely limit both the static and dynamic strength of the part. The accurate prediction of the final shape of a formed part and its residual stress state are therefore essential to the design and performance of composite structures.

Fig. 1: Typical roll formed profiles.

Generally, models of forming processes for thermoplastic composite systems only consider one phase of the material. In the case of forming the matrix remains in a molten state and the material behaviour is considered to be viscous [4,5], or more generally viscoelastic [6]. On the other hand, models which are developed to account for the distortion of a formed component as it cools from its molten state often assume thermoelastic behaviour [7]. Analytical two phase models have been suggested by Ruddock [8] and more recently by Ruddock and Spencer [9] who have developed a model which accounts for the solidification front through a cylindrical channel section in plane strain. As expected, their analysis suggests that the residual stresses and distortion may be minimised by allowing the cooling rate to tend to zero.

The present study is primarily concerned with the concept of *shape fixability*, a generic term used to define how well a component conforms to its intended geometry after deformation. To facilitate this investigation, a set of simple bending experiments has been performed. The effect of various cooling rates on the final shape of the formed strips is examined by measuring the deviation from the part's intended geometry, or *springforward*. It is to be noted that the term '*springforward*' used in this study refers to a decrease in the enclosed part angle, as opposed to '*springback*' which is commonly associated with metallic sheet. In addition to the experimental study, a numerical analysis has been undertaken in an attempt to model the effect of cooling rate on the distortion encountered during solidification and cooling. The numerical model has been formulated to account for the material property variation during cooling. Although the model makes a number of bold simplifying assumptions regarding the

material behaviour at elevated temperatures, it does serve as a useful basis for further two phase modelling using numerical techniques.

DESCRIPTION OF MODEL

The first part of the modelling to be undertaken was that of a simple thermoelastic analysis which was formulated along the same lines as the model of Zahlan and O'Neill [7]. In this analysis a 4mm thick bend region (formed to an inner radius of 10mm) was modelled as a transversely isotropic elastic solid. In keeping with their approach, the part was constructed in a cylindrical coordinate (r, θ) reference frame with supports applied along the vertical face for which $\theta = 90^\circ$. For this model the thermal loading was applied in the form of prescribed initial and final element temperatures. It should be noted that this type of loading case assumes homogenous cooling and thus ignores any thermal gradients which would be present in an actual cooling process.

In addition to the model described above, a more rigorous analysis was undertaken, involving both a transient description of the temperature variation as well as a structural analysis to compute the thermally induced stresses and strains as a function of time. The model was divided into two parts, the first dealing with the transient temperature variation in the formed part as it cooled, and secondly, an incremental stress strain analysis to compute the part's response to the applied thermal loading. The heat flux associated with the deformation was assumed to be negligible so that the transient field analysis could be performed independently. The coupling of both the field and structural analyses was performed by way of a data transfer file (DTF) as illustrated in Figure 2.

Cooling was applied to the outer surfaces of the formed part at various rates which roughly corresponded to (i) quenching, $h = 100 \text{ W/mm}^2\text{K}$, (ii) rapid cooling, $h = 50 \text{ W/mm}^2\text{K}$, and (iii) slow cool, $h = 10 \text{ W/mm}^2\text{K}$.

Fig. 2: Coupling of the transient field analysis and the structural analysis.

In order to model the two phase nature of the composite as it cooled from the melt, a number of simplifying assumptions has to be made regarding its constitutive behaviour. Ideally, the

numerical model would be formulated along the same lines as that of Ruddock and Spencer's [9] two phase model which idealises the molten phase as an 'anisotropic thermoelastic liquid'. Unfortunately this type of material definition is unavailable using many of the commercially available FE packages, including the LUSAS FE system used in this study. This meant that certain simplifying assumptions had to be made regarding the material response at elevated temperatures. It was decided that the closest approximation to the behaviour could be achieved using an anisotropic plastic hardening material model. While this assumption casts some doubts over the legitimacy of the results, particularly the development of stress in the part, it does address some of the issues regarding temperature dependent material property variation. More importantly, the model provides a basis from which further numerical modelling may be developed.

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

The experimental program consisted of a set of simple single axis, 90° bending tests which were performed using PLYTRON[®], a continuous glass fibre/polypropylene thermoplastic composite with a nominal fibre volume fraction of 35%. The single curvature bending specimens were constructed from 8 plies of prepregged sheet material giving a nominal thickness of 4mm. Figure 3 illustrates the dimensions of the samples and the intended geometry after deformation. The bending experiments were conducted over a variety of forming temperatures ranging from 180 to 140°C. In each case the same heating sequence was adopted; namely the samples were heated initially to 180°C and held for a period of 10 minutes. Once a stable environment had been reached each sample was cooled in a controlled manner to the desired forming temperature. After the specimen was formed to 90°, the strip was cooled using one of three cooling rates: i) slow (~2 °C/min) ii) moderate (~15 °C/min) iii) rapid (~60 °C/min). The cooling rate in each sample was monitored by a K-type thermocouple embedded within laminate.

Fig. 3: a) Test sample dimensions, b) Intended geometry of deformed sample.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result of the thermoelastic analysis is illustrated in Figure 4 where the springforward effect is demonstrated as the bend region cools from a forming temperature of 180°C to room temperature. Since the formed part is not constrained by any tooling and consists entirely of unidirectional plies, the solution is independent of any of the specified elastic material parameters. The numerically predicted result is a change in the enclosed part angle of approximately 1.5° which is well short of the experimentally observed results detailed in Table 1. Somewhat surprisingly, the springforward in these experiments was found to be largely independent of the forming temperature. On the other hand the applied surface cooling rate was found to significantly influence the final shape, suggesting that the majority of the

distortion was incurred as the material underwent a phase change and subsequently cooled to room temperature.

The relationship commonly used to predict the springforward in anisotropic materials formed to angle θ can be simply written as

$$\Delta\theta = (\alpha_r - \alpha_l)\theta\Delta T \quad (1)$$

where ΔT is the temperature range over which cooling takes place and α_r and α_l are the coefficients of thermal expansion in the radial and longitudinal directions respectively. The poor agreement between the experimental results and equation (1) raises some interesting questions, particularly in light of the results of Zahlan et al. [6] who achieved good correlation with CF/PEEK material. Two interesting differences to note when comparing PP and PEEK composites are the respective temperatures at which they are processed, and also the material behaviour as they cool. PEEK is typically processed at around 400°C and exhibits a viscous type of behaviour over a relatively short temperature range when cooling from the melt. In other words the material remains essentially elastic over the majority of the cooling stage. On the other hand, PP composite materials have a relatively wide forming window and can be processed at temperatures as low as 110°C during cooling before they begin to solidify [2]. Only during a relatively short proportion of the cooling stage does the material behave like an elastic solid. It is therefore suggested that for the class of composite used in this study, a thermoelastic model by itself may be insufficient to predict the distortion incurred during cooling. The material property variation, a result of transient temperature field, necessitates a more complex model which can account for the transitional behaviour between the molten and solid phases.

Fig. 4: Springforward predicted by the thermoelastic model upon cooling.

Table 1: Springforward of formed parts for various forming temperatures and cooling rates.

Cooling Rate	Forming Temperature				
	140°C	150°C	160°C	170°C	180°C
Slow	6.0°	5.9°	5.4°	5.3°	5.5°
Moderate	-	-	-	-	6.3
Rapid	-	-	-	-	7.4

From the results detailed in Table I, it is clear that the cooling rate has a significant influence on the magnitude of the springforward. With this in mind a thermo-mechanically coupled analysis was undertaken in an attempt to model this effect. The results of this analysis are presented in Figure 5. The distortion, or springforward $\Delta\theta$, has been plotted against the applied surface cooling rate. As the cooling rate is increased, it can be seen that the model begins to describe the response more effectively than the thermoelastic model. Although the trend is favorable, the magnitudes of the distortions are still considerably lower than what was observed experimentally. In light of the assumptions made regarding the material behaviour, this is understandable and a revised description of the thermorheological response may well give better correlation to the experimental results.

Fig. 5: Effect of cooling rate on spring forward in PLYRON sections formed to 90°.

The emphasis of this paper has been on modelling the springforward phenomenon which represents a physically measurable quantity. The residual stress state of a part is also an important quantity which affects the integrity but is infinitely more difficult to measure in a practical sense. While no attempt has been made here to characterise the stress state of the parts formed in these experiments, the residual stresses have been shown by others to be relatively slight in comparison to those values reported for carbon fibre/PEEK [10]. Cuff suggests that this might well be a result of the glass transition temperature T_g of PP being well below room temperature [10]. It is interesting to note that over three quarters of the residual stress in CF/PEEK is developed between T_g and room temperature [11]. It could be argued that realisation of the intended shape of a component manufactured from PLYTRON may be more of a concern than the internal stresses within the actual part.

Distortion of formed parts is something that cannot be avoided due to the elevated processing temperature requirements of thermoplastic composites. However, with the clever use of numerical modelling tools it can be predicted and accounted for at the design stage of a process. This is very important and could significantly reduce the time and expense associated with trial and error approaches. Like other processes, roll forming must address the issue of shape fixability if quality profiles, which meet strict tolerances are to be produced. As in standard die forming operations, the rolls, like the dies, may be exactly designed to account

for the distortion, or springforward incurred during cooling. For instance a set of rolls may be designed to underbend a particular section, as shown in Figure 6, in anticipation that it would adopt its desired shape upon cooling. In addition, the cooling rate may be conveniently managed by applying external heating or cooling devices between each forming station to alleviate large thermal gradients which have been shown in this study to also significantly influence the final shape of a component.

Fig. 6: Distortion of channel section (a) underbent shape prior to cooling, (b) final shape after cooling.

The implications of these results are extremely important from a manufacturing perspective as they indicate that increased conformance of a shaped component may be achieved by allowing it to cool at a relatively slow rate during the solidification period. Accepting that a cooling rate which approaches zero is both practically and economically unfeasible, the key issue that faces producers of real parts would seem to be how fast can a component be cooled without compromising its integrity. While the answer to this depends on the particular circumstances, it seems appropriate to point out, that for the class of material investigated in this study, the thermorheological behaviour has a significant bearing on the final shape of the part. Lastly it is important to note that the results presented here should not detract from the obvious benefits these materials possess, however they do point towards the need to consider very carefully the effect that cooling rate has on the shape fixability.

CONCLUSIONS

A set of simple bending tests have been performed on strips of directional glass fibre/polypropylene composite to determine the effect of forming temperature and cooling rate on the resulting distortion. The springforward in each strip was observed to be largely independent of forming temperature but highly dependent on the applied cooling rate. Samples cooled at a rapid rate were found to distort to a greater extent than samples which were allowed to cool slowly.

A finite element analysis has also been performed in an attempt to model the experimentally achieved springforward results. The first analysis idealised the formed part as a thermoelastic orthotropic solid. Unlike the results obtained for carbon fibre/PEEK, the correlation between the model and experimental results was unacceptably poor with an under prediction of around 3.5° . This has been attributed to the material property variation, a result of the transient temperature field, around the solidification period. Further modelling was then undertaken in an attempt to account for the temperature and material property variation in the part. The results of this analysis proved to be more effective in terms of modelling the cooling rate dependence although the magnitudes obtained failed to match with those achieved experimentally. It should be noted that this type of analysis appears to be extremely difficult

to tackle using many of the commercially available FE packages. However the model presented here does provide a useful basis for further work to be undertaken in this area.

The results indicate the use of slower cooling might be beneficial in producing parts with greater conformance to that of their intended geometry. This has to be acknowledged by manufacturers using materials such as PLYTRON which possess many other advantages, including lower melt temperature and a significantly large processing window.

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